

**EXPLORING THE RIDE-HAILING SERVICE QUALITY
AND RE-RIDE INTENTION OF BANGLADESHI ZOOMERS:
A PLS-SEM APPROACH**

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Abstract

The purpose of the study is to explore the nexus between ride-hailing service quality and re-ride intention of Zoomers in Dhaka, Bangladesh, with a focus on how satisfaction mediates the nexus. A structured questionnaire was distributed to 300 respondents using a convenience sampling approach, and 250 were considered valid for data analysis. PLS-SEM was employed to analyze the measurement and structural model and data analysis was done using SmartPLS 4.1.1.3. The findings showed that reliability and assurance have a positive relationship with re-ride intention (RRI) of Zoomers, while empathy, responsiveness and tangibility were determined to be statistically insignificant. Additionally, the findings revealed that Zoomers satisfaction (ZS) was significantly influenced by reliability, responsiveness, and tangibility, while dimensions such as assurance and empathy exhibit negative correlations with satisfaction. Also, the ZS as mediator significantly impacts the relationship among re-ride intention with reliability, responsiveness, and tangibility dimensions. Future researchers might consider other variables like price sensitivity, digital trust, and gender differences, and compare generational differences across different service sectors in Bangladesh.

Keywords: Service Quality, Zoomers Satisfaction, Re-ride intention, Ride-hailing, PLS SEM, Bangladesh.

1. Introduction

The Zoomers, often mentioned as the Z Generation (abbreviated as Gen Z, born between the mid to late 1990s), are characterized by their substantial reliance on digital technology, social media, and progressive ideas, and have attracted the consideration of researchers in the services offered by online platforms (Wajdi et al., 2024). Ride-hailing is such a platform that is popular among the Zoomers since it integrates the riding services with online booking, payment, review, and complaint options, facilitating real-time connections between passengers and riders, radically

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enhancing city transport by offering connectivity in the last mile (Kumar et al., 2022). With their heavy reliance on mobile applications and a preference for convenience and affordability, Zoomers have become key users of ride-hailing platforms. Therefore, it is essential to study the quality of customer service offered by ride-hailing platforms.

The study of the service quality of ride-hailing platforms is particularly significant for Dhaka city, owing to many issues. Dhaka, characterized by its high population density and severe traffic congestion, encounters considerable transportation difficulties. Ride-hailing services like Uber, Pathao, and Obhai have experienced significant popularity in recent years, offering a handy alternative to traditional taxis, which are sometimes unavailable or unreliable during peak hours (Hasan et al., 2021). By evaluating the service quality of these platforms, governments and firms may get insights into customer preferences and pinpoint areas for enhancement, like minimizing wait times, enhancing vehicle conditions, and assuring safety (Islam et al., 2023). These enhancements will elevate client satisfaction and mitigate escalating issues regarding air pollution, traffic congestion, and the necessity for more effective urban transportation solutions in Dhaka.

Ride-hailing services possess significant appeal for Zoomers for several reasons. Primarily, Zoomers prioritizes ease and efficiency, and ride-hailing services offer immediate access to transportation with a few taps on their smartphones, eliminating lengthy delays or intricate booking procedures. Secondly, this generation is exceptionally proficient with technology, and their adeptness with digital platforms increases their propensity to embrace services that smoothly incorporate technology into their everyday routines (Francis & Hoefel, 2018). Moreover, ride-hailing systems provide flexibility regarding cost and availability, rendering them suitable for the on-demand lifestyle prevalent among many Gen Z consumers (Djafarova & Bowes, 2021). Moreover, ride-hailing systems offer transparency and control over the trip experience (e.g., real-time driver tracking, selection of route kinds), catering to the need for personalized and efficient services.

Research on the RRI of Zoomers users within the framework of ride-hailing services in Dhaka is becoming increasingly crucial. Zoomers constitutes a substantial portion of this user demographic owing to their extensive smartphone utilization, inclination towards app-based services, and expectations for efficiency, customization, and dependability (Francis & Hoefel, 2018). Comprehending the factors that motivate their purpose to reuse these services is essential, since re-ride behavior signifies enduring happiness, brand loyalty, and service sustainability.

Furthermore, Zoomers exhibits a pronounced sensitivity to quality, price transparency, and user experience, demonstrating a greater propensity than older consumers to transition to other platforms when unhappy (Djafarova & Bowes, 2021). As this generation grows more economically engaged, their transportation preferences will progressively influence the need for digital mobility solutions. Consequently, recognizing the determinants particularly the elements of service quality that affect customers' decisions to persist with a ride-hailing service, is

essential for providers seeking to maintain user retention in a competitive and dynamic market. Research in this domain enhances operational strategies and service delivery while facilitating urban mobility planning by harmonizing private-sector solutions with the anticipation of the expanding youth demographic in the city.

The efficacy of ride-hailing services can be measured by assessing users' overall satisfaction through various factors, including reliability, safety, security, empathy, assurance, comfort, and tangibles (Chaudhry et al., 2018; Kumar et al., 2022; Masele & Shayo, 2024). In this context, ride-hailing services such as Uber, Pathao, Obhai, and Shohoz are increasingly appealing, presenting a possible solution to alleviate choking and deliver seamless travel (Rana et al., 2025). Ride-hailing service quality plays a pivotal role in shaping user satisfaction, which, in turn, influences RRI (Johnson & Lee, 2023). High service quality, encompassing factors such as ride comfort, driver professionalism, and convenience, can significantly enhance user satisfaction, motivating repeat usage (Wireko-Gyebi et al., 2024). The importance of these factors lies in their direct correlation with user satisfaction, which has been identified as a crucial determinant of customer loyalty and repeated use of services (Cheng & Zhang, 2023). Specifically, high service quality can lead to higher levels of satisfaction, which subsequently increases the probability of RRI. This is particularly relevant for younger users who tend to prioritize convenience, efficiency, and trust in digital services (Borges et al., 2022).

Thus, exploring the relationship between service quality and RRI through satisfaction becomes essential for understanding not only the dynamics of ride-hailing use but also the broader implications for future service improvements and market strategies (Teo et al., 2018). Nonetheless, a significant research gap exists in the literature concerning the indirect role of customer satisfaction in the link between service quality and Zoomers' RRI, particularly in the realm of ride-hailing services (Ali et al., 2022; Ma & Liu, 2019; Addo et al., 2025). Still, there is a dearth of research that directly addresses how customer satisfaction and the quality of ride-hailing services affect Zoomers' intentions to re-ride. This study pursues to fill this gap by evaluating the relationships among ride-hailing service quality, satisfaction, and RRI among Zoomers, providing insights into their preferences and behaviors in the ride-hailing market.

The goals of the study are to measure the association between the ride-hailing service quality and Zoomers' RRI, to evaluate the association between ride-hailing service quality and Zoomers' satisfaction (ZS), to test the link between ZS and RRI; and to evaluate the mediating effect of ZS in the affiliation between the ride-hailing service quality and Zoomers' RRI.

The remainder of the paper is structured as follows. The theoretical framework, literature review and research hypotheses are discussed in Section 2. This is followed by research methodology, including data gathering techniques and analytical methods including measurement and structural model analysis utilizing PLS-SEM in Section 3. The results of the hypotheses test are presented in Section 4. Discussion about the relationship between Zoomers' RRI and the quality of ride-hailing services is

elaborated in Section 5. Subsequently, Section 6 presents the conclusions including limitations and recommendations for further study.

2. Literature Review and Hypotheses Development

2.1 Social Exchange Theory

Social Exchange Theory (SET), proposed by Homans (1958) and further developed by Blau (1964), provides a fundamental framework for comprehending interpersonal and consumer connections as reciprocal trades designed to optimize benefits and minimize costs. In consumer behavior, SET has proven crucial in elucidating how perceived value and reciprocity influence enduring relationships between consumers and service providers (Cropanzano & Mitchell, 2005). Ride-hailing services like Uber, Pathao, Obhai, and Shohoz illustrate the transactional dynamics of the digital economy, where continuous user engagement relies on the perceived equity of exchanges, obtaining excellent service quality in exchange for money (Cheng et al., 2018). Service quality in ride hailing includes several characteristics such as dependability, responsiveness, driver conduct, car cleanliness, and technical user-friendliness (Parasuraman, Zeithaml, & Berry, 1988; Thaithatkul et al., 2021). Customer satisfaction, under this paradigm, occurs when the perceived quality of service meets or surpasses expectations, hence enhancing the perceived fairness of the transaction (Oliver, 1999; Kim et al., 2018).

Moreover, SET establishes a framework for comprehending RRI, characterized as the consumer's propensity to use a certain ride-hailing platform again, as a logical result of advantageous cost-benefit assessments. Customers are more inclined to exhibit loyalty and advocacy when they consider the long-term advantages of ongoing usage to surpass the related expenses (Blau, 1964; Cropanzano & Mitchell, 2005; Chen & Li, 2020; Shao et al., 2022).

2.2 Theory of Service Quality

The SERVQUAL model, an acronym for Service Quality, serves as a prevalent framework for assessing the quality of service through the analysis of the disparity between customer expectations and their actual experiences (Parasuraman et al. 1985). In accordance with the SERVQUAL model, the attributes of reliability, assurance, tangibles, empathy, and responsiveness are considered the five most important aspects of service (Shetu & Hamid, 2021). Numerous studies, including those by Islam et al. (2024), Shetu and Hamid (2021), Sikder et al. (2021), and Aseres and Sira (2020), have explored various aspects of service quality and client satisfaction within the context of ride-hailing services. Within the domain of ride-hailing services, SERVQUAL has been utilized extensively to assess service quality and customer satisfaction (Islam et al., 2024).

The reliability aspect was found to be the significant factor in customer satisfaction in a current study (Islam et al., 2024; Sikder et al., 2021 and Aseres & Sira, 2020). From the viewpoint of travelers, reliability means that rides arrive consistently and on time, with minimal deviations from anticipated schedules. This encompasses the commitment that drivers will consistently comply with established service levels and

safety standards (Islam et al., 2024). Then, the research examined ride-hailing services, revealing that responsiveness plays a crucial role in customer happiness, as identified by Arteaga-Sánchez et al. (2020). In app-based ride-hailing services, responsiveness includes prompt response to ride requests, punctual driver arrival, and prompt issue resolution (Islam et al., 2024). Recent research shows that service quality responsiveness directly affects client happiness (Islam et al., 2024; Sikder et al., 2021; Aseres & Sira, 2020).

Tangibility significantly affects client happiness, according to findings from transportation pooling platforms (Arteaga-Sánchez et al., 2020). Customer satisfaction is primarily affected by how tangible the service quality factor is, according to a recent study (Aseres & Sira, 2020). The study examines how tangibility affects service quality in Bangladeshi app-based ride-hailing services (Kumar et al., 2022). Next, assured clients possess trust and confidence in the enterprise to deliver optimal services (Sumi & Kabir, 2021). Arteaga-Sánchez et al. (2020) assert that assurance significantly impacts customer happiness in ride-hailing systems. The research by Islam et al. (2024) and Sikder et al. (2021) found that assurance adversely affects customer happiness. Finally, according to Parasuraman et al. (1985), firms that demonstrate empathy understand and handle the difficulties and worries of their clients. According to studies by Islam et al. (2024) and Sikder et al. (2021), customer satisfaction with ride-hailing services tends to decline when drivers fail to demonstrate empathy. Therefore, prior research showed that customer satisfaction is significantly and favorably affected by the empathy construct of the service quality dimension.

2.3 Ride-hailing Service Quality

Service quality has become a crucial factor in determining customer satisfaction, loyalty, and continuous use as the ride-hailing industry becomes more competitive (Thaithatkul et al., 2021; Shao et al., 2022). To evaluate and enhance service quality, researchers and practitioners commonly use the SERVQUAL model, created by Parasuraman, Zeithaml, and Berry (1988). This model outlines fundamental facets of perceived service quality, empathy, tangibility, responsiveness, assurance, and reliability. For ride-hailing to provide accurate and dependable service, reliability is an essential component (Parasuraman et al., 1988), which includes accurate estimated arrival times, punctuality of drivers, and the platform's dependability in assigning rides, which can damage consumer trust (Thaithatkul et al., 2021).

Then, tangibility describes ride-hailing service features, such as the state of the car, the look of the driver, and the user interface of the mobile app. A clean, well-maintained vehicle, a professional driver, and a functional app interface enhance customers' perception of service quality (Thaithatkul et al., 2021; Liu et al., 2021). Next, the responsiveness dimension shows how eager and capable the system or service provider is to assist users and deliver timely service. Quick app feedback, real-time driver updates, and efficient client service are all examples of responsiveness in ride-hailing. User confidence is increased by responsiveness, particularly in challenging or time-sensitive circumstances (Kim et al., 2018).

After that, assurance adds to clients' sense of security by encompassing the expertise, civility, and reliability of service providers. Particularly in markets where security is a concern, platforms that prioritize safety features like GPS tracking and emergency contact buttons strengthen the assurance dimension (Dias et al., 2019). Finally, understanding client requirements and providing individualized attention are essential components of empathy. Empathy in ride hailing is demonstrated by the way drivers comply with particular passenger demands, behave politely, and allow the platform to adjust to the preferences of each user (Tussyadiah, 2016). Customization and customer-focused features, including ride preferences or feedback systems, further enhance this dimension.

2.4 Ride-hailing Service Quality and Re-ride Intention Relationship

The correlation between the quality of ride-hailing services and users' propensity to re-engage with them is a major subject of scholarly attention. In ride-hailing systems, factors including reliability, safety, responsiveness, usability, price, and driver behaviour are frequently used to assess service quality (Yeo et al., 2017). In addition, higher customer satisfaction because of perceived service quality is consistently linked to greater RRI (Tontini et al., 2024; Ismail et al., 2023). Akbar et al. (2021) found that the quality of ride-hailing services significantly impacts customer satisfaction, which subsequently affects their intention to reuse the service. Thus, the following hypotheses can be formed:

H1: The Service quality of ride-hailing positively affects the RRI of Zoomers.

H1a: There is a positive association between assurance and the RRI.

H1b: There is a positive affiliation between empathy and the RRI.

H1c: There is a positive correlation between tangibility and the RRI.

H1d: There is a positive relationship between reliability and the RRI.

H1e: There is a positive link between responsiveness and the RRI.

2.5 Ride-hailing Service Quality and Zoomers Satisfaction

Gen Z's opinion of ride-hailing quality is heavily influenced by SERVQUAL aspects, particularly reliability, responsiveness, and assurance (Parasuraman, Zeithaml, & Berry, 1988). ZS with ride-hailing services is significantly impacted by reliability, according to a related study by Arteaga-Sánchez et al. (2020). Having grown up in the digital age, Gen Z places a high value on seamless technology and the usability of mobile apps. According to studies, Gen Z consumers want user-friendly interfaces, quick reaction times, and in-app capabilities like GPS tracking, fare estimates, and real-time updates (Liu et al., 2021; Singh & Dangmei, 2016). In addition, according to research, Zoomers place a higher priority on speed and convenience when scheduling trips on demand than they do on price alone (Francis & Hoefel, 2018). According to Hu et al. (2019), ZS is also strongly correlated with service reliability, including ride safety and driver professionalism. Features including travel history, preferred driver choices, personalized notifications, and reward programs (Wood,

2020) raise their engagement and satisfaction. Thus, we can write the following hypotheses:

H2: Ride-hailing service quality positively affects ZS

H2a: There is a positive association between ride-hailing service assurance and the ZS.

H2b: There is a positive connection between ride-hailing service empathy and the ZS.

H2c: There is a positive relationship between ride-hailing service tangibility and the ZS.

H2d: There is a positive link between ride-hailing service reliability and the ZS.

H2e: There is a positive relation between ride-hailing service responsiveness and the ZS.

2.6 Zoomers Satisfaction and Re-ride Intention Relationship

De Oña et al. (2015) indicated that higher levels of customer satisfaction are strongly associated with an increased intention to reuse the service. When Gen Z is satisfied with these functional and experiential elements, they are more likely to continue to use the same ride-hailing platform because they value smooth digital interactions, quick service, and dependability (Shao et al., 2022). Gen Z customers frequently utilize the app's usability, real-time tracking, booking ease, and system responsiveness to gauge their level of satisfaction (Liu et al., 2021). These components create a positive feedback loop that strengthens re-ride inclinations in addition to promoting instant satisfaction. The Expectancy-Confirmation Theory and the SET both state that happy consumers are inclined to stick with a business because they believe they received a fair value exchange (Oliver, 1999; Cropanzano & Mitchell, 2005). In addition to transactional factors, emotional satisfaction, such as feeling heard, appreciated, and safe by the service provider, also affects Gen Z's re-ride behaviour (Francis & Hoefel, 2018). According to studies, Gen Z passengers are more likely to suggest the service to their friends, rebook rides, and remain loyal even when prices fluctuate when they are satisfied (Wang et al., 2020). According to Shao et al. (2022), among tech-savvy urban consumers, satisfaction substantially predicted their propensity to use ride-hailing services again.

H3: ZS with Ride-hailing service and Re-ride Intention are positively related

2.7 Relationship between Ride-hailing Service Quality and Re-ride Intention with the effect of Zoomers Satisfaction

Jen et al. (2011) investigated the relation between perceived value, customer happiness, service quality, and the likelihood that passengers would use the service again. The results showed that while perceived value is the main predictor of passenger reuse intention, customer satisfaction acts as a mediator between service quality and passenger reuse intention. Service quality and corporate image have a significant influence on customer satisfaction, which in turn promotes passenger

loyalty, according to Yilmaz and Ari's (2017) analysis of the relationships between service quality, complaints, customer satisfaction, and passenger repurchase intention. Chou and Kim (2009) discovered in their research that service quality positively influenced customer satisfaction and significantly affected future reuse intentions. The study found that service quality, including functional, technical, comfort, cleanliness, and planning, positively impacts reuse intention by enhancing customer satisfaction, which in turn influences passengers' repurchase intention (Wang et al., 2020).

H4: ZS mediates the connection between Ride-hailing Service Quality and RRI

H4a: ZS mediates the association between ride-hailing service assurance and RRI;

H4b: ZS mediates the connection between ride-hailing service empathy and RRI;

H4c: ZS mediates the affiliation between ride-hailing service tangibility and RRI;

H4d: ZS mediates the link between ride-hailing service reliability and RRI; and

H4e: ZS mediates the relationship between ride-hailing service responsiveness and RRI

The link between the variables derived from the hypotheses is depicted in the hypothesized model (Figure 1) that follows. In this case, the dependent variable, RRI, as indicated by H1, is directly impacted by the independent variables of assurance, empathy, tangibility, reliability, and responsiveness. Next, H2 demonstrated the impact of service quality dimensions on ZS. H3 then demonstrated ZS's direct impact on RRI. Lastly, H4 demonstrated ZS's mediating role in the relationship between quality dimensions and RRI.

Figure 1: Hypothesized Model

3. Methodology

3.1 Participants and Procedure

This work employed exploratory research to assess Zoomers perceptions and satisfaction with ride-hailing services in Dhaka, Bangladesh. The population

encompasses the complete set of individuals, occurrences, or items that are the focus of investigation. Five items from the constructs were incorporated into the SERVQUAL element (Parasuraman et al., 1985), and the pricing fairness was modified to meet the requirements of this investigation. The study on ride-hailing services in Bangladesh used a convenience sampling method to gather data from participants. We sent 300 questionnaires to respondents via Google Form, and 250 completed questionnaires were retained after scrutiny.

Out of the 250 responses, it was found that 170 (68%) were male and 80 (32%) were female persons from Zoomers (see Table 1). The largest group of Zoomers 185 (74%) were familiar with ride-hailing as a results most of the Zoomers frequently use ride-hailing 2-3 times in a week 217 (86.8%) and 4-5 times 24 (9.6%) in a week. Results showed that 190 (76%) of the respondents were happily recommended to others using ride-hailing services in Bangladesh.

Table 1: Respondents' Profile

	Frequency	Percentage
Gender		
Male	170	68%
Female	80	32%
Total	250	100%
Level of Acquaintance		
Yes	185	74%
No	65	26%
Total	250	100%
Frequency of Use		
2-3 times	217	86.8%
4-5 times	24	9.6%
Over 8 times	9	3.6%
Total	250	100%
Future Direction		
Yes	190	76%
No	60	24%
Maybe	0	0%
Total	84	100.0%

Source: Field Survey

3.2 Measurement

A structured questionnaire with a 5-point likert-type scale was utilized to collect responses from Zoomers. A 4-item assurance scale were derived from Sikder et al. (2022) and Islam et al. (2024). Item such as “the behavior of the cab-driver will please the passenger” was utilized. A 5-item empathy scale taken from Sikder et al. (2022). It includes item like “rider understand customer needs”. A 3-item reliability scale was taken from Sikder et al. (2022). It includes item like “They provide their services at times promised”. A 4-item responsiveness scale was taken Aseres & Sira. (2020). Item such as “rider respond to request”. A 3-item tangibility scale was taken from Sikder et al. (2022). Item such as “ride-hailing apps are visually appealing”. A 4-item Re-ride Intension scale was taken from Cheah et al. (2020). Item such as “the Zoomers intends to utilize or acquire the ride-hailing service”. A 5-item ZS scale was taken from Sikder et al. (2022). It includes item like “service has lived up to my expectations”.

4. Results

The results of the current investigation are presented in Tables 1 through 11. In order to gauge how well the respondents comprehended the concept of information ride-hailing, the researcher examined their gender, level of acquaintance with green ride-hailing, frequency of use, shared interest in ride-hailing, and future suggestions for scheduling ride-hailing.

4.1 Measurement Model

The measurement model was evaluated to confirm the internal consistency, convergent validity, and discriminant validity of the latent variables. The standardized factor loadings of all items on their respective constructs were examined. According to Hair et al. (2021), a threshold of 0.70 was used to indicate acceptable item reliability, and the values of the items in this study surpass the threshold. Figure 2 displays the loading from the measurement model.

Figure 2: Measurement Model

Notes: AS-Assurance, EM-Empathy, RL-Reliability, RS-Responsiveness, TN-Tangibility, RRI-Re-ride Intention, and ZS-Zoomers Satisfaction

Table 2: Factor loading, reliability, and AVE assessment

	Loading	Cronbach's alpha	Composite reliability	AVE
<i>Assurance</i>		0.868	0.873	0.718
AS_1	0.826			
AS_2	0.879			
AS_3	0.891			
AS_4	0.789			
<i>Empathy</i>		0.826	0.866	0.631
EM_1	0.737			
EM_2	0.886			
EM_3	0.747			
EM_4	0.798			
<i>Reliability</i>		0.843	0.782	0.683

RL_1	0.766			
RL_2	0.885			
RL_3	0.825			
<i>Responsiveness</i>		<i>0.865</i>	<i>0.783</i>	<i>0.688</i>
RS_1	0.818			
RS_2	0.796			
RS_3	0.856			
RS_4	0.846			
<i>Tangibility</i>		<i>0.867</i>	<i>0.870</i>	<i>0.790</i>
TN_1	0.898			
TN_2	0.896			
TN_3	0.873			
<i>Re-ride Intension</i>		<i>0.843</i>	<i>0.846</i>	<i>0.679</i>
RRI_1	0.847			
RRI_2	0.820			
RRI_3	0.806			
RRI_5	0.823			
<i>Zoomers Satisfaction</i>		<i>0.873</i>	<i>0.878</i>	<i>0.664</i>
ZS_1	0.832			
ZS_2	0.823			
ZS_3	0.857			
ZS_4	0.729			
ZS_5	0.829			

Notes: AS-Assurance, EM-Empathy, RL-Reliability, RS-Responsiveness, TN-Tangibility, RRI-Re-ride Intention, and ZS-Zoomers Satisfaction

Then, two indicators were used to assess internal consistency reliability, Cronbach's Alpha, having a threshold of ≥ 0.70 and Composite Reliability, having a threshold between 0.70 and below 0.95 (Nunnally & Bernstein, 1994; Hair et al., 2021). The findings indicate that all constructs have values consistent with the threshold, indicating satisfactory internal consistency without redundancy (see Table 2). Ultimately, Average Variance Extracted (AVE) served as a tool to assess convergent validity. A value of 0.50 or higher for AVE signifies that the construct accounts for more than half of the variance of its indicators (Fornell & Larcker, 1981). AVE

values are above 0.50 for all the constructs under the study (see Table 2). Discriminant validity was examined using two methods, Heterotrait-Monotrait Ratio (HTMT) and Fornell-Larcker Criterion. Initially, the HTMT values that fall below 0.90 suggest sufficient discriminant validity (Hair et al., 2021). The data presented in Table 3 indicates that the maximum value recorded is 0.854.

Table 3: HTMT – List

	Assurance	Empathy	Re-ride Intention	Reliability	Responsiveness	Tangibility	Zoomers Satisfaction
AS							
EM	0.097						
RRI	0.480	0.052					
R	0.506	0.097	0.820				
RS	0.122	0.432	0.132	0.110			
T	0.297	0.080	0.416	0.404	0.080		
ZS	0.519	0.054	0.790	0.854	0.137	0.341	

Notes: AS-Assurance, EM-Empathy, RL-Reliability, RS-Responsiveness, TN-Tangibility, RRI-Re-ride Intention, and ZS-Zoomers Satisfaction

The Fornell-Larcker Criterion indicates that the square root of each construct's AVE must exceed its highest correlation with any other construct's validity (Hair et al., 2021). Results showed that the AVE has a higher correlation value than the other constructs (see Table 4). Hence, all the constructs exhibit favourable levels of discriminant validity.

Table 4: Fornell-Larcker criterion

	AVE	Assurance	Empathy	Reliability	Responsiveness	Tangibility	RRI	ZS
Assurance	0.718	0.847						
Empathy	0.631	-0.012	0.794					
Reliability	0.683	0.327	-0.092	0.827				
Responsiveness	0.688	0.050	0.357	-0.071	0.829			
Tangibility	0.790	0.261	-0.126	0.419	-0.079	0.889		
RRI	0.679	0.364	0.031	0.662	0.031	0.410	0.824	
ZS	0.664	0.297	-0.132	0.722	0.044	0.449	0.678	0.815

Notes: RRI-Re-ride Intention and ZS-Zoomers Satisfaction

4.2 Structural Model

The structural model was evaluated using Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modeling (PLS-SEM) with SmartPLS 4.1.1.3 At first, collinearity diagnostics were

performed by examining the Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) values. In Table 5, VIF values below 5 are considered acceptable, indicating the absence of severe multicollinearity among predictor constructs (Hair et al., 2021).

Table 5: Collinearity Statistics

VIF	
Assurance -> RRI	1.155
Assurance -> ZS	1.152
Empathy -> RRI	1.183
Empathy -> ZS	1.160
Reliability -> RRI	2.243
Reliability -> ZS	1.299
Responsiveness -> RRI	1.199
Responsiveness -> ZS	1.156
Tangibility -> RRI	1.320
Tangibility -> ZS	1.253
ZS -> RRI	2.309

Notes: AS-Assurance, EM-Empathy, RL-Reliability, RS-Responsiveness, TN-Tangibility, RRI-Re-ride Intention, and ZS-Zoomers Satisfaction

The explanatory power of the model was subsequently evaluated through the coefficient of determination (R^2), reflecting the proportion of variance in the endogenous variable that is accounted for by its predictors. As suggested by Cohen (1988), R^2 values of 0.75, 0.50, and 0.25 can be described as substantial, moderate, and weak, respectively. The obtained R-squared values are presented in Table 6. As indicated by the results, RRI accounted for 54.5% of ZS and 56.7%.

Table 6: Coefficient determinant test

	R-square	R-square adjusted
RRI	0.545	0.534
ZS	0.567	0.558

Notes: RRI-Re-ride Intention and ZS-Zoomers Satisfaction

To test the significance and strength of the relationships, PLS-SEM was employed, using bootstrapping procedures with 5,000 resamples to generate t-values and p-values for each hypothesized path. A t-value greater than 1.96 and a p-value less than

0.05 indicate that the path coefficient is statistically significant at the 5% level (Hair et al., 2021). The path coefficient value is utilized to test hypotheses, as summarized in Table 7. H1a evaluates that assurance does significantly impact RRI ($\beta= 0.126$, $t = 2.636$, $p = 0.008$). Hence, H1a is accepted. H1b is also rejected, since there is no statistically significant impact of empathy on RRI ($\beta= 0.049$, $t = 0.788$, $p = 0.431$). However, reliability has a significant impact on RRI ($\beta= 0.325$, $t = 4.427$, $p = 0.000$). Thus, H1c is accepted. Again, there is no significant effect of responsiveness on RRI ($\beta= -0.031$, $t = 0.478$, $p = 0.633$), rejecting H1d. But H1e is not accepted ($\beta= 0.076$, $t = 1.384$, $p = 0.166$), indicating tangibility has no significant effect on RRI.

The hypothesis H2a, which posits that assurance has a negative effect on ZS ($\beta= 0.036$, $t = 0.758$, $p = 0.448$), has been rejected. H2b is also rejected ($\beta= -1.000$, $t = 1.695$, $p = 0.090$), indicating that empathy has no significant effect on ZS. Once more, reliability has a significant impact on ZS ($\beta= 0.639$, $t = 13.561$, $p = 0.000$). Thus, H2c is accepted. Nevertheless, H2d is accepted, since there is a statistical impact of responsiveness on ZS ($\beta= 0.137$, $t = 2.057$, $p = 0.040$). Again, H2e is accepted because there is a statistical impact of tangibility on ZS ($\beta= 0.170$, $t = 3.259$, $p = 0.000$). However, H3 is accepted ($\beta= 0.366$, $t = 4.388$, $p = 0.000$), suggesting that ZS has a significant impact on RRI.

Table 7: Direct effect

	B	σ	t	p	Decision
<i>H1a Assurance -> RRI</i>	0.126	0.048	2.636	0.008	Accepted
<i>H1b Empathy -> RRI</i>	-0.031	0.064	0.478	0.633	Rejected
<i>H1c Reliability -> RRI</i>	0.325	0.073	4.427	0.000	Accepted
<i>H1d Responsiveness -> RRI</i>	0.049	0.062	0.788	0.431	Rejected
<i>H1e Tangibility -> RRI</i>	0.076	0.055	1.384	0.166	Rejected
<i>H2a Assurance -> ZS</i>	0.036	0.047	0.758	0.448	Rejected
<i>H2b Empathy -> ZS</i>	-0.100	0.059	1.695	0.090	Rejected
<i>H2c Reliability -> ZS</i>	0.639	0.047	13.561	0.000	Accepted
<i>H2d Responsiveness -> ZS</i>	0.137	0.066	2.057	0.040	Accepted
<i>H2e Tangibility -> ZS</i>	0.170	0.052	3.259	0.001	Accepted
<i>H3 ZS -> RRI</i>	0.366	0.083	4.388	0.000	Accepted

Notes: AS-Assurance, EM-Empathy, RL-Reliability, RS-Responsiveness, TN-Tangibility, RRI-Re-ride Intention, and ZS-Zoomers Satisfaction

The analysis of the indirect effect presented in Table 8 reveals a significant outcome, H4a is rejected ($\beta = 0.013$, $t = 0.752$, $p = 0.452$), indicating that assurance on RRI through ZS is statistically insignificant. Again, H4b was also rejected ($\beta = -0.036$, $t = 1.494$, $p = 0.135$), indicating that the relationship between empathy on RRI through

ZS is statistically insignificant. Once more, there is a positive relationship between reliability on RRI through ZS; H4c is accepted ($\beta = 0.234, t = 4.149, p = 0.000$). On the other hand, H4d is accepted ($\beta = 0.050, t = 1.974, p = 0.048$), indicating that responsiveness on RRI through ZS is statistically significant. Again, there is a significant effect of tangibility on RRI through ZS ($\beta = 0.062, t = 2.815, p = 0.005$), accepting H4e. Figure 3 displays the research framework according to the analysis, which includes the path coefficients.

Table 8: Indirect effect

	B	σ	t	P	Decision
H4a Assurance -> ZS -> RRI	0.013	0.017	0.752	0.452	Rejected
H4b Empathy -> ZS -> RRI	-0.036	0.024	1.494	0.135	Rejected
H4c Reliability -> ZS -> RRI	0.234	0.056	4.149	0.000	Accepted
H4d Responsiveness -> ZS -> RRI	0.050	0.025	1.974	0.048	Accepted
H4e Tangibility -> ZS -> RRI	0.062	0.022	2.815	0.005	Accepted

Notes: RRI-Re-ride Intention and ZS-Zoomers Satisfaction

Figure 3: Tested Model

Notes: AS-Assurance, EM-Empathy, RL-Reliability, RS-Responsiveness, TN-Tangibility, RRI-Re-ride Intention, and ZS-Zoomers Satisfaction

5. Discussion

The aim of the study was to find out the relationships between ride-hailing service quality and RRI of Zoomers. The study found that assurance and reliability dimensions positively affect the Zoomers RRI. Assurance has a substantial influence on RRI of Zoomers ($t = 2.636$, $p = 0.008$). The result is different from the previous studies Sharma & Lambert (2013); Lee et al. (2018); Parasuraman et al. (1988); Afthanorhan et al. (2019); Ray et al. (2021). Zoomers are more inclined to use the service again as they view the platform as a representation of dignity, respectful conduct from drivers, and trendy professionalism. In addition, reliability demonstrates a significant positive effect on the RRI of Zoomers ($t = 4.427$, $p = 0.000$). The findings from earlier investigations, Siddiqui et al. (2022) and Oliveira et al. (2020), indicate a positive correlation between reliability and RRI. Zoomers are more likely to re-ride because they perceive the platform as reliable, saves time and friction.

In contrast, empathy, responsiveness and tangibility are not positively affecting the re-ride intention of Zoomers. The results found that the nexus between empathy and RRI of Zoomers is not statistically significant ($t = 0.788$, $p = 0.431$). Previous studies, Priporas et al. (2017) and Sharma & Das (2017), reveal that there is a positive relationship between empathy and RRI. The reasons could be the unnecessary conversation, such as asking personal questions, offering life advice, fear or discomfort among female Zoomers. Again, there is no relationship between responsiveness and RRI of Zoomers ($t = 0.478$, $p = 0.633$). Prior studies, Choudhury et al. (2021), Arteaga-Sánchez et al. (2020) & Sharma & Das (2017) show a positive relationship between responsiveness and RRI of Zoomers. But, the reasons could be unnecessary calls or excessive questions from a driver may cause inconvenience. Finally, tangibility has no positive impact on RRI of Zoomers ($t = 1.384$, $p = 0.166$). Research found that Arteaga-Sánchez et al. (2020) and Sharma and Das (2017) show a positive relationship between tangibility and RRI of Zoomers. These reasons could be the physical attributes like car branding, driver uniforms and denying digital payments.

The study also proposed to analyze the role of ZS in the relationship between service quality and RRI. In the hypothesis H2a, results ($t = 0.758$, $p = 0.448$) indicate assurance has no positive association with ZS in Bangladesh. Research conducted by Alam et al. (2022), Khan & Rahman (2021), and Hossain & Jahan (2020) revealed equivalent findings. Zoomers can detect inconsistencies between verbal assurance and actual performance, preventing cognitive dissonance and lower satisfaction when drivers or platforms fail to deliver on their promises and also create mistrust and anxiety among female users. Following that, ZS and empathy are not positively correlated ($t = 1.695$, $p = 0.090$). Research by Djafarova & Trofimenko (2019) and Alam et al. (2022) has produced similar findings. The lack of professionalism and interpersonal interaction during rides to prevent discomfort could be the cause, while over-empathy could feel intrusive because of gender dynamics or safety issues. On the other hand, reliability has a positive association with ZS ($t = 13.561$, $p = 0.000$).

Prior research by Hossain & Jahan (2020), Chowdhury & Alam (2023), and Djafarova & Trofimenko (2019) discovered a favourable correlation. The reasons for ZS, such as real-time driver tracking, fare estimates, punctuality, accurate ETAs, and timely arrival, are crucial in congested cities like Dhaka.

However, responsiveness and ZS are positively correlated ($t = 2.057$, $p = 0.040$). Prior research by Chowdhury and Alam (2023), Djafarova and Trofimenko (2019) and Hossain & Jahan (2020) has produced similar findings. Zoomers are satisfied due to effective complaint handling and timely app feedback and support, and apps should be responsive during, before, and after service to enhance ZS. Also, tangibility and ZS are positively correlated ($t = 3.259$, $p = 0.000$). Research by Alam et al. (2022), Gentina and Parry (2016), and Islam et al. (2023) found a positive association. The factors contributing to the ZS include driver professionalism, vehicle cleanliness, branding, visual appeal, and user-friendliness. The subsequent hypothesis H3 demonstrates an outcome of ($t = 4.388$, $p = 0.000$), indicating that ZS significantly affects RRI. Similar research outcomes have been found in the research of Khan & Rahman (2021), Gentina & Parry (2016) and Priporas et al. (2017). The satisfaction of Zoomers significantly influences their intention to re-ride, as it enhances both emotional and functional trust.

Moreover, the hypothesis results for analyzing the mediation effect of assurance on RRI through ZS ($t = 0.752$, $p = 0.452$) were statistically insignificant. Previous studies by Khan & Rahman (2021) and Djafarova & Trofimenko (2019) reveal a positive association. The reasons could include inauthentic communication, boundary violations, concealment of ineptitude, and gender or cultural suspicion. Again, the mediation relationship between empathy on RRI via ZS is not statistically substantial ($t = 1.494$, $p = 0.135$). Parallel research findings have been seen in the studies conducted by Gentina & Parry (2016) and Alam et al. (2022). The reasons could include the unprofessional behaviour of the driver and not accepting digital payment. Then, the mediation relationship between reliability on RRI through ZS is statistically significant ($t = 4.149$, $p = 0.000$). Research findings from Khan & Rahman (2021), Siddiqui et al. (2020), and Alam et al. (2022) are congruent with the current study. The RRI of Zoomers through ZS significantly affects the consistent performance, behavioural loyalty, and emotional stress during travel, especially in congested urban areas such as Dhaka.

Furthermore, the mediation relationship between responsiveness on RRI through ZS is statistically significant ($t = 1.974$, $p = 0.048$). Previous studies conducted by Priporas et al. (2017) and Hossain & Jahan (2020) have yielded comparable findings. The reasons could be that efficient customer service and driver punctuality boost satisfaction, making Zoomers more likely to reuse the service. Finally, the mediation effect of tangibility on RRI through ZS ($t = 2.815$, $p = 0.005$) is statistically significant. Previous research by Siddiqui et al. (2020), Khan & Rahman (2021) and Djafarova & Trofimenko (2019) found similar findings. The reasons could be visually based judgements, professionalism, and safety, which strongly influence satisfaction and, consequently, the RRI of Zoomers in Bangladesh.

6. Conclusions and Future Directions

Drawing from the SERVQUAL framework, encompassing reliability, responsiveness, assurance, empathy, and tangibility, while positive relationships were found between RRI and service quality attributes like reliability and assurance, negative effects were observed for empathy, responsiveness and tangibility, highlighting that Zoomers prefer a low-contact, efficient, and tech-driven experience over high-touch or overly formal service.

Again, the findings reveal that ZS is significantly influenced by certain service quality dimensions, notably reliability, responsiveness, and tangibility, while dimensions such as assurance and empathy exhibit weaker or even negative correlations with satisfaction. Zoomers prioritize efficiency, speed, hygiene, and technological integration over interpersonal interactions; they value reliable service performance, quick response times, and clean vehicles, which indicates a generational shift in service expectations. Once more, the findings demonstrate that ZS is a significant predictor of RRI of ride-hailing services in the Bangladeshi young generation. Significant elements impacting satisfaction, including service reliability, app usability, pricing transparency, and driver behavior, were identified as having a strong effect on the probability of future usage.

Next, the mediation findings suggest that certain service quality factors, particularly reliability, responsiveness, and tangibility, have a significant positive mediation effect on ZS, which in turn strongly predicts their intention to re-ride. While dimensions like assurance and empathy show weaker associations with satisfaction and RRIs, it is clear that Zoomer riders prioritize performance-based and tangible aspects of service delivery over emotional or relational components.

This study has several limitations that should be considered when interpreting the findings. First, the research focuses exclusively on Zoomers. For deeper insight into the preferences and behaviors of younger users, future research could incorporate perceptions of Millennials, Gen X, or older ride-hailing customers. Second, the study relies on self-reported data collected through a structured questionnaire. Future research can capture responses from riders. Third, the cross-sectional research design captures perceptions and intentions at a single point in time. Future research could expand this study by incorporating longitudinal data or comparing generational differences across other service sectors. Finally, the study examines selected dimensions of ride-hailing service quality and does not include all possible factors that may influence RRI. Future research could expand the model by incorporating variables such as price sensitivity, digital trust, or gender-based differences for a more nuanced understanding of Gen Z's consumption behavior in the on-demand mobility sector.

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